

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX ACID. PART I. DECOMPOSITION OF AMMONIUM MOLYBDATE WITH NaOH AND HCl

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The decomposition by HCl of a molybdic acid salt with a weak base (i.e. ammonium molybdate) has been studied electrometrically and otherwise and the results are compared with those of its salt with a strong base (i.e. sodium molybdate) under similar conditions. The nature of the decompositions is shown to be the same in both cases, higher and higher polysalts being formed with increasing addition of HCl. But the rapid rise of conductivity and (H^+) (hydrogen ion concentration) beyond the stage $R_n[O(MoO_3)_4]$ ($R = Na$ or NH_4) is considered to be due to the formation of an acid molybdate $RH[O(MoO_3)_4]$. The action of NaOH on ammonium molybdate having the composition $(NH_4)_x[O(MoO_3)_y]$ has been studied electrometrically and it is shown that the anion of this salt gradually breaks into a normal one $[O(MoO_3)]$ and then NH_4^+ ion is displaced from the salt by Na^+ ion; from the curves, NH_4^+ ion can be estimated. The formation of higher polymolybdates from normal ones has been described in terms of electronic structure.

A number of oxides such as silica, vanadium pentoxide, molybdenum and tungsten trioxides possess definite acidic properties and forms normal salts, yet they exhibit abnormal changes during neutralisation of their acids or acidification of their normal salts.

The abnormal behaviour of sodium molybdate during acidification received the attention of the early workers. Thus Rosenheim and Berthelm (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 34, 427; 1906, 54, 320) prepared the acid and acid salts from a normal sodium molybdate. Dumanskii and collaborators (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 38, 208) employed measurements of electrical conductivity and depression of freezing points to study the mode of displacement of the acid from sodium molybdate by HCl, while Britton and German (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2154) studied its decomposition by strong and weak acids conductometrically and potentiometrically using quinhydrone electrode in the latter case. It appears from their results that in the acidified solution, sodium molybdate exists in the form of polymolybdates whose composition depends on the strength and concentration of the acid used. The polymolybdates formed after the stage $Na_n[O(MoO_3)_{n+1}]$ are not stable towards HCl and undergo decomposition with the liberation of highly ionised polymolybdic acid in solution. But Jander and collaborators (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 413; *Metall-berse*, 1930, 20, 1855) from similar studies concluded that the salt, Na_nMoO_n , first goes over to a salt of trimolybdic acid followed by aggregates containing 6, 12, 24, etc. molybdenum atoms. Bevan (*Chem. Soc. Annual Reports*, 1943, p. 53) from glass electrode p_x and conductivity measurements showed that polymolybdates or tungstates of the type $R_n[O(MoO_3)_n]$ are salts of very strong acids. This is responsible for the polysalts not decomposing completely even in excess of HCl in dilute solutions.

The degree of decomposition, dissociation, hydrolysis etc. of a salt depend on the strength of the component acid and base on the one hand and $[H^+]$ of the system on the other. The behaviours of sodium molybdate (i.e. salt of molybdic acid with a strong base) during acidification with strong and weak acids, as exhibited in electrometric studies, are known. It is desirable that the behaviour of a molybdic acid salt with a weak base

should be studied under similar conditions in order that more light may be thrown on the nature of the complex acid. Ammonium molybdate has been selected for the purpose, because it is not only the salt of a weak base but also, unlike Na^+ ion, it offers the additional advantage that the basic NH_4^+ ion associated at any stage with the acidic anion can be estimated by easy analytical method. Dhar and collaborators (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, 174, 135; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 441) in their work on "Dialysis, ultrafiltration and coagulation of molybdic acid sol" used ammonium molybdate and HCl or HNO_3 for the preparation of the sol, but its exact composition has not received attention.

EXPERIMENTAL

The potentiometric titration and p_H measurements were in all cases carried out with glass electrode prepared from corning glass No. 015 (MacInnes and Dole, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 29). A thin bulb showing interference colour only of this glass was blown at the end of a resistance glass tube and tested for its asymmetry E.M.F. and resistance. The one giving constant values of E.M.F. with buffer solutions and of resistance low enough for E.M.F. to be measured with an accuracy of ± 1.0 millivolts was selected for our experiments. The conductometric titration and conductivity measurements were done as usual using a drum roller meter-bridge (Leeds and Northrup). The temperature of the solutions was kept constant at 25° by immersing them into a thermostat while measurements were being made.

The reagents HCl and NaOH were C.P. grade quality and in making solutions, conductivity water was always used. The starting material, ammonium molybdate (B.D.H. pure) was recrystallised and analysed for its compositions. The ammonia content in the solution was estimated by the micro-Kjeldahl method and MoO_3 content by gravimetrically precipitating as MoS_3 and weighing as MoO_3 (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", 1935, Vol. II, p. 274). The mean of five estimations are: NH_3 , 8.42% and MoO_3 , 80.0%; ratio MoO_3/NH_3 , 9.59. This percentage composition demands the formula of the material to be $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{2.4}]$, for which the value of the ratio MoO_3/NH_3 should be 9.6. A corresponding sodium salt of the same composition was isolated by Rosenheim (*loc. cit.*).

In the titrations three sets of readings were taken, all at 25° ; p_H or conductivity was measured after necessary addition of the titre in different glass stoppered bottles (i) immediately after proper mixing, (ii) after ageing for 48 hours at room temperature (25°), (iii) after boiling for 20 minutes at 85° and then cooling. Only readings from (i) and (iii) are represented in the graphs; those from (ii) always assumed more or less intermediate values.

Reaction between Ammonium Molybdate and Caustic Sols.—In Fig. 1 (curves 1 and 1') are represented the results obtained conductometrically by titrating 25 c.c. of ammonium molybdate solutions (6.0518 g. and 4.0412 g. per litre) with 0.665 *N.* and 0.33 *N.* NaOH respectively. The corresponding potentiometric titration results are shown similarly in Fig. 1 (curves 2 and 2'). Several such titrations of the molybdate at different concentrations varying from 2.0 to 10.0 g. per litre were carried out; the respective curves were of the same nature as shown in Fig. 1. It may be noted here that ageing or heating the mixtures before taking readings had no appreciable influence on the course of any curves.

FIG. 1

Conductometric and potentiometric titrations of Am-molybdate with NaOH.

Decomposition of Ammonium Molybdate by Hydrochloric Acid.—In Fig. 2 (curve 1) are represented the potentiometric results obtained by titrating 50 c.c. of NH_4 -molybdate solution (9.978 g. per litre) with 0.2956 *N*-HCl. In Fig. 2 (curve 2) are shown the corresponding conductometric results. The dotted lines show the course of readings taken after immediate mixing and the thick lines correspond to those recorded after heating and cooling at each stage. It will be noticed that the latter had the pronounced effect of making the inflexion sharp.

Dialysis of Acidified Ammonium Molybdate Solution.—To about 1000 c.c. of 0.2-0.3 *M* (with respect to MoO_3) solution of NH_4 -molybdate, more than two equivalents of HCl diluted with water were added and after waiting for sometime the mixture dialysed in a parchment bag placed in a large porcelain basin, supplied with a current of distilled water at 50° . The presence of Cl^- ion in the solution was tested with AgNO_3 solution acidified with HNO_3 . After two days the sol in the bag was found to be free from Cl^- ion. While the sol was under the process of further dialysis, some 40 c.c. sol were sampled out from the bag occasionally and analysed for its NH_3 and MoO_3 contents. This was continued for sometime until the concentration of MoO_3 in the sol was very low. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I

MoO ₃ (in 25 c.c. sol).	Amount of NH ₃ .	Ratio $\frac{\text{MoO}_3}{\text{NH}_3}$.	Probable composition.
0.1151 g.	3.3140 × 10 g.	35.1	(NH ₄) ₂ [O(MoO ₃) _{2.4}] or NH ₄ H[O(MoO ₃) _{1.2}]
0.0925	2.8090	34.5	(NH ₄) ₂ [O(MoO ₃) _{1.7}] or NH ₄ H[O(MoO ₃) _{1.05}]
0.0698	1.9940	33.0	(NH ₄) ₂ [O(MoO ₃) _{1.4}] or NH ₄ H[O(MoO ₃) _{0.7}]
0.0339	0.9740	34.1	(NH ₄) ₂ [O(MoO ₃) _{1.7}] or NH ₄ H[O(MoO ₃) _{1.05}]
0.0231	0.6503	35.5	(NH ₄) ₂ [O(MoO ₃) _{1.8}] or NH ₄ H[O(MoO ₃) _{0.9}]

DISCUSSION

Reaction between NH₄-Molybdate and NaOH

Potentiometric studies (Fig. 1, curves 2 and 2') show that in the very beginning there is a diffused inflexion, after which the p_H of the system changes only slowly with the addition of NaOH and finally terminates with a sharp inflexion. The course of the curve can be explained by assuming reactions to take place as follows:

The first diffused inflexion is due to the rapid removal of H^+ ions already present in the solution by the probable hydrolysis of the polymolybdate (i). As NaOH is gradually added, polymolybdic acid is liberated more and more to be neutralised forming normal sodium molybdate. This reaction becomes complete by the transformation of the poly-salt into a normal one. Further addition of NaOH increases the $[OH^-]$ considerably to show the sharp inflexion observed. That titre values corresponding to this sharp inflexion coincide with the stoichiometric amount demanded by (ii) above, and are shown in Table II below.

TABLE II

Mols. of $(NH_4)_2O(MoO_3)_{2.4}$.	Mols. of NaOH (calc. from eqn. ii).	Mols. of NaOH corresponding to the final inflexion in curves.
5.923×10^{-4}	16.50×10^{-4}	16.38×10^{-4}
4.789	13.26	12.29
3.548	9.936	9.908
2.369	6.633	6.667
1.184	3.314	3.333

The corresponding conductometric studies (Fig. 1, curves I and I') show that the conductivity of the solution begins to increase linearly in the beginning with gradual addition of NaOH and afterwards there is a nearly flat region of slight diminution of conductivities followed by sharp increase as would be done by free NaOH. Thus we observe here two breaks, the first one coincides with the final inflexion point of the corresponding potentiometric curve and obviously this must be associated with the end-point of the reaction represented by eqn. (ii). The flat portion is evidently due to the formation of slower moving ions in the solution resulting from the addition of NaOH. This can be ascribed to the reaction :

After reaction shown in eqn. (ii) is over, double decomposition between NaOH and $(NH_4)_2[O(MoO_3)]$ begins to take place, when NH_4^+ ion, associated with the molybdate ion, is displaced by Na^+ ion from NaOH. We have seen previously that the p_n of the system increases considerably when the reaction (ii) was over and as such the liberated weakly basic NH_4^+ ion will remain completely unionised. Thus the part previously played by the faster moving NH_4^+ ion (mobility at 25° is 74.8) in conducting current,

TABLE III

Mols. of $(NH_4)_2O(MoO_3)_{2.4}$	Mols of NaOH calc. by eqn. (iii).	Mols. of NaOH from 2nd break in curves.	Mols. of NaOH equiv. to the diff. between 1st and 2nd breaks.	Calc. mols. of NH_4 in soln.
5.923×10^{-4}	28.43×10^{-4}	29.26×10^{-4}	12.62×10^{-4}	12.51×10^{-4}
4.789	22.74	22.76	10.09	10.02
3.548	17.03	17.22	7.49	7.508
2.369	11.37	11.09	5.06	5.008
1.184	5.68	5.61	2.48	2.506

was taken over by the slower moving Na^+ ion (mobility at 25° is 50.1). During this process of substitution of NH_4^+ ion by Na^+ ion, the resulting conductivity of the solution diminishes. When it is over, still further addition of NaOH causes conductivity to increase considerably. If so, the added NaOH equivalent to the 2nd break here should be equal to the stoichiometric amount demanded by eqn. (iii), as shown in Table III above. The difference between the 1st and 2nd breaks can alternatively be taken as equivalent to the amount of NH_4^+ ion present in the solution.

It will be noticed that the amount of NaOH equivalent to the 2nd break agrees well with the amount calculated from eqn. (iii) and also the difference between the 1st and 2nd breaks fairly equals the calculated amount of NH_4^+ ion present in the solution. It was also observed that the titration of the same NH_4 -molybdate solution with NaOH using phenolphthalein as indicator showed the same end-point as the final inflexion or 1st break of the respective potentiometric and conductometric titrations.

Decomposition of NH_4 -Molybdate with HCl

Potentiometric studies (Fig. 2, curve 1) show that $[\text{H}^+]$ slowly increases in the beginning and then rapidly with an inflexion near about p_n 3.0. If it is assumed that HCl added has gone into complete reaction, the composition of the molybdate at the point of inflexion will be $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4.2.2.2}]$. The corresponding conductometric studies (Fig. 2, curve 2) similarly demonstrate that there is no appreciable change of conductivities in the beginning until the composition of the molybdate corresponds to $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4.2.2}]$ and thereafter there is a rapid and uniform increase as would be the case with free HCl .

The course of the curves is interpreted as follows:—when HCl is added to NH_4 -molybdate solution, the partly liberated molybdic acid in the solution is immediately taken up by the parent salt left unreacted to form a polymolybdate, thus,

The value of x in the complex will depend on the $[\text{H}^+]$ of the solution. The polymolybdates that are formed in the beginning have got the same conductivity as their parent salts and this is true until the composition of the salt becomes $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4.2.2}]$, when still more HCl was added, the conductivity and $[\text{H}^+]$ of the resulting solution increased rapidly.

Starting with Na -molybdate under similar conditions, Dumanskii and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) found that after the addition of 1.6 moles of HCl per mole of Na_2MoO_4 , there was sudden increase in the difference between the freezing point depression of actual reaction mixture and of a theoretical mixture made up on the assumption of simple double decomposition. Britton and German (*loc. cit.*) also starting with Na_2MoO_4 and HCl got similar inflexions electrometrically after the composition $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4.2.2}]$ was reached, and they assumed that the sodium tetramolybdate was decomposed by HCl liberating the corresponding acid $\text{H}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$ which ionised strongly in solution to show increased conductivity. But Jander and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) came to somewhat different conclusions.

In the case of Na-molybdate it was shown that the specific conductivities at the same dilutions of the molybdate varying from Na_2O , MoO_3 to Na_2O , 4MoO_3 , do not differ appreciably from each other but for still higher polysalts the values appear to be much greater as shown in Table IV_A below, where the specific conductivities of the solutions of the solid salts at different dilutions at 25° are reproduced from Britton and German (*loc. cit.*) [these data being compiled by them from the records of Walden (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1887, 1, 529), Rosenheim (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1916, 96, 139) and Rosenheim, Felix and Pinkser (*ibid.*, 1913, 70, 292)]. In Table IV_B are given the corresponding data on equivalent conductivity as calculated by the author. The dilutions (in litres) refer to volumes containing 1 g. atom of sodium.

TABLE IV_A

Dilution	32	64	128	256	512	1024
$\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)]$	3.14	1.66	0.87	0.45	0.23	0.12
$\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{1\frac{1}{2}}]$	3.09	1.70	0.91	0.49	0.26	0.14
$\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$	3.05	1.69	0.84	0.51	0.28	0.16
$\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_3] (?)$	6.15	4.74	2.73	1.48	0.79	0.40

TABLE IV_B

Dilution	32	64	128	256	512	1024
(1) $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)]$	100.5	106.3	111.4	115.2	117.8	122.8
(2) $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{1\frac{1}{2}}]$	98.9	108.7	116.5	125.4	133.1	143.2
(3) $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_2]$	98.9	108.1	120.3	130.5	143.4	163.9
(4) $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_3] (?)$	106.8	303.4	349.4	378.8	404.4	409.7
or $\text{NaH}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$						
Diff. (4)—(3)	97.9	195.3	229.1	248.3	261.0	245.8

In the above table the conductivities of the salts up to the tetramolybdate have nearly the same value but the supposed octamolybdate has considerably higher value. It will be noticed that the difference between the equivalent conductivities of the tetra- and octa-molybdates, except at the dilution 32, assumes values which will be obtained if one H^+ ion is generated in the solution of the Na-tetramolybdate at the expense of Na^+ ion (the difference between the ionic mobilities of H^+ and Na^+ at 25° is 349.7—50.1, i.e., 299.6).

From this it appears that the composition of the solute, which was supposed by Britton and Rosenheim as Na-octamolybdate, should more reasonably be represented as $\text{NaH}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$. The salt isolated, and designated as $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_3]$ and used for measurements of electrical conductivity by Rosenheim and Felix (*loc. cit.*) was obtained from an acidified solution of sodium molybdate. This should be represented by the alternative formula $\text{NaH}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$. As a matter of fact Rosenheim and collaborators (*loc. cit.*) thought that it could be represented as an acid salt $\text{NaH Mo}_4\text{O}_{13}$.

Accordingly we must ascribe the considerable increase in conductivity and $[\text{H}^+]$ after the composition $\text{Na}_2[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4-3}]$ or as in the present case of $(\text{NH}_4)[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_{4-3}]$, to the formation of an acid molybdate corresponding to $\text{RH}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$ where $\text{R}=\text{Na}$

or NH_4 . The analytical results (Table I) for the composition of the solute of the molybdate acid sol after careful purification by dialysis, show that the value of this ratio MoO_3/NH_4 obtained, can definitely be associated with the formula $\text{NH}_4\text{H}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_4]$. Thus molybdic acid sol, as we have obtained under the stated conditions, contains the acid molybdate partly in molecularly dispersed state, i.e. in true solution and partly in polymerised or aggregated state as micelle ions or colloidal particles of the composition $\{\text{NH}_4\text{H}[\text{O}(\text{MoO}_3)_n]\}_n$.

In keeping with the electronic theory of valency we can picture the decomposition of normal molybdate by an acid to form gradually higher polymolybdate, thus,

Salt of normal
molybdic acid.

Salt of bimolybdic
acid.

Salt of higher
polymolybdic acid,
where n may be 2, 3, 4, etc.

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